

AN INSIDER’S HISTORY OF THE WIKIMEDIA MOVEMENT: A WORK IN PROGRESS

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Abstract

This study offers preliminary insights from a meta-historiography of wikimediam scholarship, examining how insider histories published over the past 24 years frame the Wikimedia movement’s history. This research is part of an ongoing PhD project entitled *Knowledge Equity at Wikimedia*.

Introduction

Cultural History is underrepresented in Wikimedia research. Yet skills central to this field—archival inquiry, cultural mediation, and storytelling—are evident in community practices. As organizers, wikimedians engage in meta-discussions on historical evolution and shared memory; as communicators, they assist newcomers and outsiders in making sense of the movement’s history. Historical culture surfaces in published works, including Wikipedia manuals, academic theses, and critical reviews. In this corpus, wikimediam authors assume a historiographical role informed by lived experience and practical engagement. While few are professional historians, most are interdisciplinary scholars acting as historians by trade—but all share an approach shaped by their nativeness to the digital encyclopedic ethos. This study conceptualizes such contributions as insider histories and experiments in the historian’s craft, examining how wikimedians document, interpret, and theorize their movement’s history.

As a work in progress, the research will ultimately situate these practices within broader debates in Public Digital History, activist research, and the Wikimedia movement’s pursuit of Knowledge Equity. The questions below guide the investigation but cannot be fully addressed at this stage.

Research Questions

RQ1: How do insider histories of the Wikimedia movement align with or challenge historiographical frameworks, particularly concerning authorial authority and the articulation of past-present-future? And how does Public Digital History intersect with these considerations?

RQ2: How do wikimediam scholars balance participation and objectivity in documenting their movement’s history? How does this relate to research activism and the Knowledge Equity strategy?

Methodology

Drawing on Chitu Okoli’s methods of Systematic Literature Review and Theoretical Concept Synthesis (Okoli, 2015; 2022), I conduct a meta-historiography of the Wikimedia movement, examining how wikimediam scholars embodied the *historian’s craft* in communicating *insider histories*—narratives based on participant or informed observation. Rather than synthesizing findings, the study analyzes the methodological approaches in the selected literature.

A reproducible protocol guided the literature survey, conducted in January 2025. The analysis was conducted independently, without a formal review team, as part of my doctoral research. It covered published works without restrictions on time period or language, excluding conference proceedings. Databases searched included Google Scholar, Google Books, JSTOR, I-Share Libraries, Scopus, and Web of Science. Main keywords were Wikimedia or Wikipedia; combined for books with *anthropology*, *ethnography*, *history*, or *sociology*; and for papers and book chapters with *community*, *contributor**, *editor**, *movement* or *user**, and *fieldwork*, *interview**, *observation**, *questionnaire**, or *survey**. The words *classroom*, *teach**, *student**, *reader**, and *quality* were excluded in all cases to ensure relevance.

Inclusion criteria prioritized insider perspectives, analytical depth, and a systemic focus on the Wikimedia movement. Included studies employed qualitative methods, such as observation, interviews, and surveys, while addressing aspects like community practices, governance, and strategy. In contrast, works primarily using quantitative methods and/or focused on content analysis and single-event cases (e.g., classroom projects, edit-a-thons) were excluded. From an initial corpus of 525 items, 58 were selected for analysis: 9 books and 49 papers or chapters.

The literature analysis proceeds in three phases. Phase one, presented here, examines selected books: one handbook (Ayers et al., 2008); two collections (Lovink & Tkacz, 2011; Reagle & Koerner, 2020); and seven analytical studies (Lih, 2009; Dalby, 2009; O’Sullivan, 2009; Reagle, 2010; Jemielniak, 2014; McDowell & Vetter, 2021). Phase two will examine the remaining items, papers and book chapters, while phase three will manually incorporate additional sources identified throughout the previous phases.

Preliminary Insights

Taking a longitudinal view of the nine books analyzed in the first phase of this study, all focus on the English Wikipedia, with one being a comparative approach (Jemielniak, 2014). Yet each engages with the broader Wikimedia ecosystem beyond the encyclopedia, to varying degrees. The notion of a social movement is uneven across the corpus, reflecting shifts in publication context in the mid-2010s: early works refer to “communities” through sociological frameworks (Ayers et al., 2008; Lih, 2009; Dalby, 2009; O’Sullivan, 2009; Reagle, 2010; Lovink & Tkacz, 2011), while others explicitly frame Wikimedia as a “movement” (Jemielniak, 2014; Reagle & Koerner, 2020; McDowell & Vetter, 2021).

Across this body of work, distinct trends emerge. Between 2008 and 2009, the history of Wikipedia was often told in response to external criticism. These accounts articulated the project’s origins and ethos through comparative lenses, drawing genealogies from Antiquity, the Enlightenment, the Dot-com Bubble, and the Free and Open Source Software movement (Ayers et al., 2008; Lih, 2009; Dalby, 2009; O’Sullivan, 2009). The 10th anniversary of Wikipedia in 2011 marked a shift, opening space for more critical and reflective analyses (Lovink & Tkacz, 2011). Before and after that moment, new studies began to frame participant observation as a key to unlocking deeper insights into the global movement (Reagle, 2010; Jemielniak, 2014). This turn gave way to more systemic approaches shaped by evolving structures of global governance. On Wikipedia’s 20th anniversary, the shift from genealogy to strategy culminates in retrospective analysis as a means for articulating future visions (Reagle & Koerner, 2020). Genealogy is then recast as archaeology, as newer works excavate epistemic structures and discursive practices (McDowell & Vetter, 2021). The present study joins this archaeological front—not focused on knowledge production on Wikipedia per se, but on the history of the Wikimedia movement.

Despite the authors’ multiple voices, varied aims, and disciplinary positions, their works share a key feature: nativeness. Wikimedian scholars assume the role of interpreters, communicating the movement’s history to outsiders. They offer vivid accounts of Wikimedia’s evolution—its background, values, guidelines, local contexts, and global cultural exchange. Many of them also share a distinctive Wikipedian flair as they recount cautionary tales, ranging from edit wars and media controversy to personal experiences and collective trauma. Though they may appear as privileged knowledge, these insider histories are meticulously sourced—drawing from Wikimedia pages, mailing list archives, community reports, and multimedia files, as well as academic or press coverage, often triangulated with participant observation and interviews.

Partial Conclusions, Future Questions

The preliminary insights reveal points of contact between wikimedians’ approach to their own cultural history and Marc Bloch’s canonical work. In his unfinished book, The Historian’s Craft (1949), Bloch described history as the science of humanity¹ in time—a modernist, humanist perspective that challenged traditional emphases on dates and facts. Similarly, wikimedian scholars tend to highlight not just content or technology, but the people behind Wikimedia as a sociotechnical phenomenon (Niederer & Van Dijck, 2010).

Secondly, Bloch also warned against an excessive focus on origins, arguing that historiography should prioritize transformation. This insight proves valuable when applied to Wikimedia. While early publications followed a genealogical history of Wikipedia, recent scholarship marks an archaeological turn that favors epistemic excavation over the consolidation of foundational narratives.

A third point lies in the centrality of source analysis. Bloch insisted that even the clearest documents will only speak when they are properly questioned (Bloch, 1949: 64). Wikimedians not only question sources, but interpret them through their nativeness—writing about events in which they are directly or indirectly involved, blending past and present concerns while anticipating future implications.

Finally, there is a shared awareness of historical time pressure. In fast-evolving sociotechnical contexts, narratives may become outdated before they are even read. This raises a persistent historiographical question: can history ever be purely objective, or must it reflect the spirit of its time—being critical, situated, and action-oriented?

In the 1940s, Bloch wrote clandestinely while in the French resistance. Wikimedians, by contrast, operate with unparalleled access to sources, and benefit from feminist and decolonial critiques of objectivity. Still, it took nearly two decades for the Wikimedia movement to prioritize Knowledge Equity within the bounds of its pragmatic neutrality. This prompts further reflection: to what extent have scholarly critiques shaped Wikimedia’s meta-discussions? How were they received? Have they contributed to the strategic processes that led to the pursuit of Knowledge Equity? By 2025, the Knowledge Equity milestone has sparked meaningful initiatives. But deeper structural change remains pending—and is increasingly threatened by the global rise of anti-diversity agendas. As the world shifts, a pressing challenge emerges: how do we protect and advance this ideal? And how can history help?

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¹ Unfortunately, the original term “humanity” was framed and translated in various languages through the lens of the male as norm. (↖, ↗)

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